

Fluoride assisted stabilization of manganese(III) in aqueous medium. Synthesis and spectral characterization of new mixed-ligand fluoromanganate(III), containing hydroxy-carboxylic acids as ancillary ligands

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Abstract : Fluoride assisted stabilization of manganese(III) has been demonstrated by synthesizing new mixed-ligand fluoromanganate(III) complexes, $A_2[MnF_4(L)]$ ($A = K$, $L =$ citric acid, tartaric acid) from aqueous medium. Mixed-ligand fluoromanganate(III) complexes have been synthesized from a reaction of $KMnO_4$, 40% HF with corresponding ancillary ligands maintaining $KMnO_4 : HF : \text{ancillary ligand}$ ratio as 1 : 4 : 1. Newly synthesized complexes are stable in absence of moisture and are practically insoluble in common organic solvents. Complexes were characterized on the basis of elemental analyses, chemical determination of oxidation state, FTIR, electronic spectral studies, room temperature magnetic moment measurements and by thermal studies. The room temperature magnetic moment values for the complexes lie in the range 4.9 to 5.1 μ_B . Electronic spectral studies suggests an appreciable splitting of 5E_g ground state of manganese(III) in the complexes leading to a distorted octahedral structure.

Keywords : Fluoride assisted stabilization, manganese(III), aqueous medium.

Introduction

Manganese can exist in a number of oxidation states, and the ability of manganese to adopt a wide range of oxidation states has resulted in the metal being at the active sites of several redox enzymes¹⁻³. The tri-positive state of manganese is an enigmatic oxidation state of the metal, requires a special attention not only because of its biochemical relevance in diverse redox functions¹⁻³, or search for stable manganese(III) building blocks to be used as precursor for single molecule magnets⁴, but also because it is difficult to stabilize in aqueous medium⁵ and many of its complexes exhibit unusual magnetic and structural features⁶⁻⁸. Coordination chemistry of manganese(III) is, however, not easy to explore because of its fairly oxidizing power and easy disproportionation, thus isolation of stable solid manganese(III) complexes from aqueous medium are rather difficult to achieve. Thus selection of appropriate ligands and suitable routes for the synthesis of stable manganese(III) complexes from aqueous solution is an important pre-requisites for further studies.

There have been indications in regard of capability of

fluoride ion, hydroxy acids especially α -hydroxy acids in stabilizing manganese(III) ion in solution^{5,8,9}. Strong acidic ligand like fluoride has a pronounced stabilizing effect on manganese(III) both in solution as well as in solid state, and coordination of fluoride also introduces anti ferromagnetism in fluoromanganate(III) compounds^{6,8}. Biogenic ligands like α -hydroxy acids serve as important substrate in many biochemical processes¹⁰. Citric acid has been known for its abundance in physiological fluids and its chemical versatility towards biologically relevant metal ions¹¹. The prominent function of the citrate ion is directly related to its metal-chelating capacity which is manifested in its multimodal coordination to various metal ions of biological significance. Tartaric acid, another α -hydroxy carboxylic acid also found to react readily with many metal ions to form variety of complexes. Tartrate ligands due to their conformational flexibility and diversity in complexing behavior are also interesting for studying the self-assembled framework, as a route to novel microporous compounds¹².

The number of reported low molecular weight manganese species bearing physiologically prominent carboxy-

lic acid such as citric or tartaric acids have been measured¹³. As mentioned (*vide infra*), α -hydroxy acids might stabilize the manganese(III) oxidation level in solution, but it is expected that an introduction of F⁻ ligand would be able to contribute significantly towards stabilizing Mn^{III}- α -hydroxy acids systems, leading to an access to mixed-ligand fluoromanganese(III) complexes containing α -hydroxy acids as ancillary ligand in solid state. We report herein synthesis, isolation, spectral characterization and an assessment of structure of new mononuclear mixed-ligand fluoromanganate(III) compounds containing α -carboxylic acid as ancillary ligands.

Experimental

Materials :

The chemicals used were all reagent grade products. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Spectrum-100 FTIR spectrometer. Electronic spectra were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer model Lambda-25 spectrophotometer. The Gouy method was used to measure the magnetic susceptibility of the complexes with Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as the standard.

Synthesis of mixed-ligand fluoro complexes of manganese(III), of the type A₂[MnF₄(L)] (L = citric acid and tartaric acid, A = K) :

To an aqueous solution of 1.0 g (6.33 mmol) of KMnO₄ in 20 cm³ of water kept in an ice-bath was added 2 cm³ (40.00 mmol) of 40% HF with continuous stirring. The solution was stirred for *ca.* 10 min followed by the addition of a solution of 1.329 g (6.33 mmol) of citric acid/ 0.9491 g (6.33 mmol) of tartaric acid in 10 cm³ of water and the resultant solution was stirred for a further period of *ca.* 15 min, when a vigorous reaction sets in with evolution of carbon dioxide gas and the solution color changed from intense purple to brown. On slow addition of an equal volume of pre-cooled acetone brown microcrystal-

line product precipitated out. The compounds were collected by filtration, washed three to four times with small volume of acetone and dried *in vacuo* over conc. H₂SO₄.

Elemental analyses :

Manganese was estimated volumetrically by complexometric titration with EDTA^{14a} using Erio-T as indicator. The fluoride contents of the compounds were determined by Volhard's method^{14b}. Carbon, hydrogen were estimated by micro-analytical methods (The results were obtained from RSIC, NEHU, Shillong) (Analytical data given in Table 1).

Chemical determination of the oxidation state of manganese :

The oxidation state of manganese was determined iodometrically by the method reported in literature¹⁵.

Results and discussion

The problem associated with the synthesis of manganese(III) compounds from aqueous medium is the tendency of the metal ion to disproportionate to manganese(IV) and manganese(II)⁵. In view of the pronounced stabilizing effect of fluoride ion on manganese(III), it was anticipated that the problem associated with synthesis of manganese(III) complexes from aqueous medium may be encountered by carrying out the reaction in an acidic medium in presence of fluoride ion. It was expected that this strategy would lead to synthesis of stable mixed-ligand fluoro complexes of manganese(III) from aqueous medium. An important pre-requisite in this context is the selection of appropriate source of the metal ion, and to consider this, knowledge of redox properties of the ancillary ligand is essential. Thus when a ligand is capable of reducing Mn^{VII}, KMnO₄ may be a good starting material whereas for ligands which do not exhibit such properties a Mn^{III} species viz. MnO(OH) may be suitable. Citric acid can reduce KMnO₄ even at room

Table 1. Analytical data of the complexes

Compound	Color	Yield (%)	Magnetic moment at 300 K, μ_B	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				
				A	Mn	F	C	H
K ₂ [MnF ₄ (L)] (L = tartaric acid)	Brown	76	4.9	21.80 (21.78)	15.30 (15.36)	21.31 (21.22)	13.38 (13.40)	1.37 (1.39)
K ₂ [MnF ₄ (L)] (L = citric acid)	Dark brown	78	5.1	19.56 (19.50)	13.68 (13.75)	19.06 (19.00)	18.02 (18.00)	1.76 (1.75)

temperature, accordingly reaction was performed by reacting an ice-cold solution of KMnO_4 with 40% HF and citric acid at *ca.* 0 °C maintaining KMnO_4 : HF : citric acid ratio as 1 : 4 : 1. Vigorous reaction was initiated which resulted in reduction of Mn^{VII} by citric acid and led to the successful synthesis of manganese-fluoro-citrato complex from aqueous medium. Similar synthetic strategy led to the successful synthesis of Mn^{III} -fluoro-tartrato complex from aqueous medium. The compounds synthesized in this way were found to be brown micro crystalline products of composition $\text{A}_2[\text{Mn}(\text{L})\text{F}_4]$ (A = K, L = citric or tartaric acid). The newly synthesized compounds are stable in the absence of moisture and are practically insoluble in common organic solvents.

Magnetic moment :

The room temperature (300 K) magnetic susceptibility measurements of the complexes exhibit magnetic moment values of $\text{K}_2[\text{MnF}_4(\text{L})]$ (L = citric acid) and $\text{K}_2[\text{MnF}_4(\text{L})]$ (L = tartaric acid) complexes as 5.1 and 4.9 μ_{B} respectively. These values are normal as expected for a high spin d^4 system of manganese(III) and show that the strong antiferromagnetism usually encountered in binary fluoromanganate(III), $[\text{MnF}_5]^{2-}$ ^{7,8} is practically absent in case of the newly synthesized mixed-ligand fluoromanganate(III) complexes.

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra of freshly prepared citrato complex was recorded immediately after making an aqueous solution containing very small amount of HF. However, due to poor solubility of tartrato complex its solid state reflectance spectra was recorded. The complexes exhibit bands in the range 18240–20000 cm^{-1} and 21990–22220 cm^{-1} , assigned to ${}^5B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^5B_{2g}$ and ${}^5B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^5E_g$ modes of transition respectively¹⁶.

The observed spectral pattern is characteristic of the presence of high-spin Mn^{III} ion and suggest an appreciable splitting of 5E_g ground state of manganese(III) leading to a distorted octahedral environment around manganese(III) center¹⁶. Appearance of an intense band in the region 214 nm (46700 cm^{-1}) in the compounds may be attributed to charge transfer transitions. Thus the magnetic moment values and electronic spectral band positions unequivocally suggest the presence of high-spin Mn^{III} ion in the complexes reported herein.

Infrared spectra :

Infrared spectra of the complexes displayed well resolved spectral pattern, significant features of which are summarized in Table 2. The notable features of the infrared spectra of $\text{K}_2[\text{MnF}_4(\text{L})]$ (L = citric acid or tartaric acid) involve absorptions due to coordinated α -hydroxy acid¹⁷ and fluoride ligand¹⁸. Carboxylate ion can coordinate to a metal centre in a variety of way. The difference between $[\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{COO}) - \nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{COO})]$, $\Delta\nu$, value allows one to distinguish among the unidentate, chelating bidentate and bridging mode of coordination of the carboxylate group. Separation significantly less than that of ionic value ($\sim 164 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) is indicative of the presence of chelating and/or bridging carboxylate group, whereas separation substantially greater than the ionic mode indicate monodentate coordination¹⁹.

Citric acid can coordinate to metal centre in different fashion²⁰. Despite its potential for tridentate coordination, citric acid may also coordinate in bidentate as well as monodentate fashion. Citric acid usually employ its α -carboxylate group to coordinate to metal center at high acidic condition (pH $\sim 1-4$), however, β -carboxylate group participate in coordination in a weakly acidic condition, whereas tridentate coordination via α -carboxyl, β -carboxyl and α -hydroxy groups is observed usually in neutral condition of the reaction medium.

The notable features of IR spectrum of tartrato complex were strong absorptions at *ca.* 1587 cm^{-1} due to asymmetric carboxyl stretching frequency ($\nu_{\text{asy}}\text{COO}^-$) and corresponding symmetric ($\nu_{\text{sym}}\text{COO}^-$) stretching frequency was observed at *ca.* 1350 cm^{-1} . In case of citrato complex, IR spectrum exhibit the corresponding asymmetric ($\nu_{\text{asy}}\text{COO}^-$) and symmetric ($\nu_{\text{sym}}\text{COO}^-$) stretching modes of vibrations of carboxylate group at 1613 cm^{-1} and 1410 cm^{-1} respectively. The separation of frequency between the antisymmetric and symmetric stretching frequencies of carboxylate group, $\Delta\nu$, greater than 200 cm^{-1} ($\Delta\nu > 200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in both the complexes is typical of monodentate coordination of carboxylate group¹⁹. In addition to the observed bands, appearance of a band at *ca.* 1700 cm^{-1} in the complexes is assignable to $\nu(\text{COOH})$ ²¹ and also suggest the presence of undissociated, uncoordinated carboxylate group in both the complexes. Considering the highly acidic condition of the reaction medium (pH ~ 2) it

appears that citric acid is coordinated to Mn atom involving its α -carboxylate group (vide *infra*). The observance of a strong band at ca. 3417-3419 cm^{-1} in the compounds was assigned to stretching vibrations of hydroxyl group, $\nu(\text{OH})$. The lowering O-H stretching frequency in the synthesized complexes in comparison to that observed for free acids suggest participation of -OH group in coordination. Such modes of coordination of α -hydroxy group is well documented in literature¹⁷. Thus IR spectral data suggest an overall bidentate coordination of tartrate and citrate ion towards manganese(III) centre. The terminal mode of coordination of fluoride ligand was ascertained by observance of band in the range 415-446 cm^{-1} assigned to $\nu(\text{Mn-F})$ ¹⁸.

Table 2. Structurally significant IR bands of the complexes

Compound, band position (cm^{-1})		Assignment
$\text{K}_2[\text{MnF}_4(\text{L}_1)]$	$\text{K}_2[\text{MnF}_4(\text{L}_2)]$	
3419	3417	$\nu(\text{OH})$
1700	1720	$\nu(\text{COOH})$
1613	1587	$\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{COO}^-)$
1410	1350	$\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{COO}^-)$
415	446	$\nu(\text{Mn-F})$
353	393	$\nu(\text{Mn-O})$

L_1 = Citric acid; L_2 = tartaric acid.

Reactivity towards H_2O_2 :

An aqueous solution of the citrate complex (~ 10 mg) was treated with aqueous H_2O_2 (30%, w/w, 5 cm^3) and the mixture was stirred at 25 $^\circ\text{C}$, when minute effervescence due to liberation of O_2 was observed. The original brownish colour of the reaction mixture became colorless, however, no solid product could be obtained from the mixture.

Thermal studies :

The results of pyrolytic studies of $\text{K}_2[\text{MnF}_4(\text{L})]$ (L = citric acid) show that the compound does not lose any weight till 160 $^\circ\text{C}$ indicating non existence of lattice water in the compound. The compound on being further heated to 200-240 $^\circ\text{C}$ suffered a loss of one molecule of HF per molecule of the compound. Above 260 $^\circ\text{C}$ the complex undergo gradual decomposition due to organic moiety. The ultimate product has been found to be MnF_3 , which is known as a powerful fluorinating agent²². The results of thermal studies further support the formulation

of the compound.

Conclusion :

Fluoride assisted stabilization of manganese(III) has been demonstrated by synthesizing mixed-ligand fluoromanganate(III) complexes with α -hydroxy acids as ancillary ligand from aqueous medium. Strong antiferromagnetism encountered in binary fluoromanganate(III), $(\text{MnF}_5)^{2-}$, is practically absent in case of the newly synthesized compounds. The electronic spectral studies suggest an appreciable splitting of 5E_g ground state of Mn^{III} in the complexes. Distorted octahedral structure has been proposed tentatively for the newly synthesized complexes.

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